

On the Formation Constants of Cadmium-alanine Complexes from Polarographic Data*

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The polarographic data for cadmium-alanine complexes have been analysed by the methods of Lingane, Hume, and Ringbom and also by the solution of equations by the method of least squares and the results compared. The stability constants of the three complexes are $\log \beta_1 = 4.49$, $\log \beta_2 = 8.00$, and $\log \beta_3 = 9.49$.

A study of polarographic methods of determination of the overall complexity constants shows that the method of Lingane¹ cannot be extended to systems where more than two successive complexes are in equilibrium. This conclusion is borne out by our studies on cadmium— α -alanine complexes and also by a recalculation of the constants for cadmium— β -alanine².

EXPERIMENTAL

Current voltage measurements were made on a manual set-up using an H-cell and a saturated calomel electrode (S. C. E.) as a reference electrode. A Cambridge bench type pH-meter was used for measuring the pH of the solutions.

Cadmium nitrate (E. Merck, G. R.) and α -alanine (E. Merck), recrystallised from methanol-water mixture, were used for preparing the stock solutions. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 with potassium nitrate. No maximum suppressor was used and the pH was adjusted with NaOH solution.

Polarograms of cadmium in presence of alanine were taken at different pHs. The half-wave potentials were determined from the log-plots and the slopes indicated a two-electron reversible reduction. The concentration of the free alaninate ion (A) was calculated from the pH of the solution, the concentration of alanine, and its pK value³ of 9.86.

The method of Lingane was extended for the calculation of the complexity constants of cadmium— α -alanine complexes. The constants are recorded in Table II. The method is valid only when one complex is present over the concentration range or when the final complexity constant is desired. Complex formation proceeds in steps and two successive constants should differ by a large factor for any single species to be predominant.

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1. Kolthoff and Lingane, 'Polarography', Interscience Publishers, 1952, Vol. I, p. 211.

2. Smith *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 9, 48.

3. Keefer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2329.

When three or more complexes are present, the plot of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs. $-\log (A)$ is best represented by a curve (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1. Plot of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs. $\log (A)$.

TABLE I

Analysis of $F_j(x)$ function for cadmium- α -alanine.

Cd = 0.51mM. α -Alanine = 0.1137M. (i_d) = 2.24 μ A. μ = 0.1.

Temp. = 30 $\pm$ 0.5°. $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ = 1.8mg^{2/3} sec.^{-1/6}. ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$)_s = -0.576V vs. S.C.E.

$-\log (A)$.	$\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	i_d .	$F_0(x)$.	$F_1(x)$.	$F_2(x)$.	$F_3(x)$.
3.9	24.6mv	2.19 μ A	6.78	4.59 $\times 10^4$		
3.7	31.7		11.69	5.36		
3.6	35.5		15.66	5.84		
3.5	39.5		21.28	6.41		
3.4	44.0		30.05	7.30		
3.3	48.8		43.43	8.47		
3.2	53.8		63.74	9.94		
3.0	64.0	2.18	140.10	13.91		
2.9	69.2		208.64	16.49		
2.7	80.0		478.00	23.90		
2.3	103.5		2899.00	57.82	10.73 $\times 10^7$	
2.1	116.3	2.13	7923.00	99.74	12.06	
2.0	122.8		13230.00	132.30	12.83	
1.9*	129.8	2.08	22860.00	181.56	14.10	
1.8	136.3		37030.00	237.40	14.73	3.05 $\times 10^9$
1.7*	143.5		65390.00	327.70	16.23	3.17
1.5*	158.0		198900.00	629.00	19.77	3.13
1.4	165.5	2.08	353700.00	888.40	22.22	3.09

$$\beta_1 = 4 \times 10^4. \beta_2 = 0.99 \times 10^8. \beta_3 = 3.1 \times 10^9.$$

*Not taken into account for calculation by the method of least squares

De Ford and Hume⁴ have derived a relationship for calculating the overall complexity constants in such cases and their final equation is:

$$F_0(x) = 1 + \beta_1(A) + \beta_2(A)^2 + \beta_3(A)^3 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$= \text{antilog} \left[0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} \{ (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_o \} + \log \frac{I_s}{I_0} \right] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$F_0(x)$ values were calculated at different values of (A) from the experimental parameters (Table I). By plotting $F_j(x)$ values against (A) (Fig. 2) and extrapolating to $(A) = 0$, the values for β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 were obtained (Table II).

FIG. 2. Plot of $F_j(x)$ vs. (A) .

It may be pointed out that equations of Lingane and also equation (2) are applicable to systems containing a large excess of the ligand concentration. The actual concentration of the free ligand at the electrode surface $(A)_o$ should, however, be calculated at low concentrations⁵. At the half-wave potential, $(A)_o$ is given by

$$(A)_o = (A) - \frac{\bar{n}}{2} \frac{C_m}{2} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

4. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1951, 73, 5321.

5. Ringbom and Eriksson, Acta Chem. Scand., 1953, 7, 1105.

where C_m is the total metal concentration and $\bar{n}$, the average ligand number, is given by

$$\bar{n} = \frac{-1}{0.03} \cdot \frac{d \Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}}{d \log (A)_o} \quad (4)$$

The values of $(A)_o$ calculated from equations (3) and (4) by successive approximation, together with the $F_o(x)$ values were used for obtaining the constants by the graphical method (Table II).

TABLE II

Stability constants of cadmium-alanine complexes.

Method	β_1		β_2		β_3		Σr^2	
	$\alpha \times 10^{-4}$	$\beta \times 10^{-3}$	$\alpha \times 10^{-8}$	$\beta \times 10^{-3}$	$\alpha \times 10^{-9}$	$\beta \times 10^{-6}$	α	β
Lingane	4.70	..	1.41	..	5.75	..	5.55×10^{10}	4.73×10^9
	*13.49	5.13	0.66	3.89	1.45	7.59	2.34×10^{10}	
Hume using (A) values	4.00	2.57	0.09	2.09	3.10	4.27	2.96×10^5	7.22×10^4
Hume using (A) _q values	4.00	..	0.86	..	3.20	..	..	..
Least squares	3.08	1.00	1.00	2.69	3.07	3.89	2.53×10^5	4.37×10^4

*See reference 2.

Equation (1) representing the relation between $F_o(x)$ and (A) values in Table I has been solved by the method of least squares⁶ and the values of β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 are 5.12×10^3 , 1.00×10^9 and 3.07×10^9 respectively. Since the contribution of $\beta_1 A$ to the function $F_o(x)$ is more significant at lower concentrations of (A), only the first eight equations have been solved and the values of β_1 and β_2 are 3.08×10^4 and 1.07×10^9 respectively. The sum of the squares of the residuals, Σr^2 , is minimum for 3.08×10^4 and not for 5.12×10^3 and hence this value is accepted for β_1 .

Table II indicates that the constants obtained by the method of least squares represent the best fit for the data. The values obtained by the Humes method agree well with these values. The complexity constants accepted for the three species are $\log \beta_1 = 4.49$, $\beta_2 = 8.00$, and $\log \beta_3 = 9.49$. With these values, the percentage of different species (Fig. 3) and $\bar{n}$ (Fig. 4) have been calculated as a function of free-ligand concentration. It can be seen from Fig. 3 that at a particular concentration of free ligand (say, when $p=2$), there exists CdA^+ or CdA_3^- in addition to CdA_2 . The plot of $\bar{n}$ vs. pA also shows no distinct steps. The constants obtained by the method of Lingane are therefore less precise and the analysis of the shift in the half-wave potential in terms of $F_o(x)$ is more justifiable.

The data reported earlier for cadmium- β -alanine have also been analysed by the methods described above and the results are recorded in Table II. A value of 3.0 for $\log \beta_1$ is obtained against the reported value of 3.71.

The order for stability⁷ of the amino-acid complexes of metals is $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Zn} > \text{Co} > \text{Cd} > \text{Fe} > \text{Mn}$. Table III records the stability constants of the complexes of these metals with α - and β -alanine⁸. The values for β_1 and β_2 , obtained by the method of least squares, fit well in this sequence. The value for $\log \beta_1$ agrees well with the value of 4.2, obtained from glass electrode measurements⁹.

FIG. 3. Distribution of cadmium in different forms.

FIG. 4

TABLE III

Stability constants of alanine complexes of some metals.

	Cu.	Ni.	Zn.	Co.	*Cd.	Fe ²⁺ .	Mn ²⁺ .
α -Alanine ($\mu=0$)							
Log K_1	8.51	5.96	5.23	4.82	4.48		3.24
Log K_2	6.86	4.70	4.33	3.66	3.52		2.81
Log K_1K_2	15.37	10.66	9.56	8.48	8.00	7.3	6.05
β Alanine ($\mu = 0.1$)							
Log K_1	7.13	4.63	4.00		3.00 [†]		
Log K_2	5.47	3.40			2.43 [†]		
Log K_1K_2	12.60	8.03		~ 7 [†]	5.43 [†]	~ 4 [†]	
	‡ $\mu=0.01$.		* $\mu=0.1$		† $\mu=2.0$		

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